

EUPHEMISM IN THE PRISM OF TEXT REALITY

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Abstract. The problem of studying euphemisms is far from exhausted in Russian studies and, more broadly, in Slavic studies. To this day, there is not a single monograph devoted to substitute names in the Russian language. There are no dictionaries of euphemisms in Slavic studies (a pleasant exception to this rule is the dictionary of euphemisms of the Polish language. Interlingual comparisons of euphemisms in Slavic studies are just beginning. There is no common understanding of the boundaries of substitute names. Thus, Polish researchers are usually characterized by a broader understanding of euphemisms: they include and means of politeness (addressing you), and indirect names of God, i.e. euphemisms from the point of view of the history of the language, and not its current state.

Introduction

The problem of studying the textual functions of euphemisms is also at the stage of accumulation of material. The main function of euphemisms in the text and discourse, as you know, is mitigation. Substitutive names are used in cases when a particular word (combination of words) seems to the speaker to be rude, indecent, capable of hurting the interlocutor.

The study of euphemisms in the aspect of functional stylistics makes it possible to identify the specific textual functions of euphemisms of various functional varieties.

In a literary text, euphemisms, in addition to the main function of mitigation, productively perform an aesthetic, ornamental function. Euphemisms in a literary text can also perform the following functions: giving the language a "literary" form, creating and enhancing a humorous effect, characterizing characters, creating vivid artistic images.

Special functions are performed by euphemisms in social jargons. The main function of the jargon of the underworld is the concealment of the essence of the signified. These are the surrogates for prison, crime, drugs and their use.

The function of a language game, a joke, a pun is widespread in social jargons for euphemisms. See examples from thieves' jargon: dacha (instead of prison); bracelets (instead of handcuffs).

Discussion

Compare the euphemistic designations for vomiting in youth jargon: call Ichthyander, scare Ichthyander, hug a white friend, and more. etc. In passing, we note that if throughout the twentieth century there were two euphemisms replacing the designation of the eruption of vomiting, to go (to go) to Riga (paronymic way of formation; paronyms Riga and burp), and the outdated euphemism Friedrich heraus), then at the end of the twentieth century, and especially at the beginning of the XXI century. these euphemisms have already formed a thematic group. These are descriptive humorously ironic turns of grubs to brag about; show what was for breakfast; euphemisms-tropes, which are based on an ironic metaphor and personification associated with the toilet: scare the snow maiden (that is, scare the toilet, white as the snow maiden); cuddle with a white brother (i.e. with a toilet bowl); shouting at a white friend (i.e. screaming while suffering from vomiting into the toilet) a metaphor based on the similarity of sounds lies in the following euphemism: tease sheep (by analogy with the sounds made by sheep "be-ee-ee").

«A new euphemism appeared, formed in a paronymic way: to perform Rigoletto's aria (Rigoletto's paronyms and burp)». This one probably has a linguistic

and extralinguistic explanation. On the one hand, it is due to drastic linguistic changes: the language taste of the era has changed, speech has become more relaxed, ironic. On the other hand, there is probably an extra-linguistic factor: an increasing number of people are participating in outdoor activities, food is becoming more diverse. New habits emerge. In particular, Friday evening in the city becomes the time for the widespread use of alcoholic beverages.

Euphemisms are widespread in the texts of various functional varieties of the Russian language.

Euphemisms are productive in scientific texts. For example, the UMO sent out to universities recommendations to the reviewer of theses in a streamlined form to make an assessment: «The reviewer should not give recommendations to the SAC regarding the assessment in a four-point system». You can use the following wording: “Deserves the highest rating”, “Quite meets the requirements ...”, “Deserves 3 positive ratings ...”, etc.

Euphemisms are widespread in journalistic texts. So, a Samara football commentator who covers the achievements of the Krylya Sovetov football team notes: I don't want to talk badly about Krylya Sovetov, I want to create an image of a strong, successful team. Therefore, if a team played badly, unsuccessfully on the road, I write in my note: the team is looking for its own style.

The main purpose of euphemisms in the text «is to soften what is being reported, since a euphemism is a word or expression used instead of another, which for some reason is inconvenient or undesirable to pronounce». But in addition to the main purpose, euphemisms perform a variety of functions depending on the functional variety of the text and the text task.

Euphemisms as substitute names are part of synonyms and perform semantic and stylistic functions in textual reality. «The semantic functions include substitution and refinement functions for synonymous euphemisms». The function of substitution is performed by full synonyms of euphemism. For example: In ancient

Rome, luxurious restrooms (1) - freaks (2) - were so comfortable that they even served as a meeting place and conversations for wealthy citizens. The rest used stinking public latrines (3). Even then, ordinary Romans, apparently out of class protest, made it a habit to cover the walls of latrines (4) with drawings and inscriptions of irreverent content. «The first, third and fourth euphemisms perform the function of substitution. The function of substitution can also be performed by partial synonyms-euphemisms, if their difference is neutralized by the context».

Synonymous euphemisms also perform the function of clarification. See the example above for the second euphemism in relation to the others. «The clarification function is carried out, as a rule, by ideographic synonyms and direct forbidden names, which are in the same context as optional euphemisms». Under optional euphemisms, we mean substitute names that are not due to a strict prohibition. «These are such euphemisms as limping (instead of limping); gets sick (instead of getting sick), does not hear (about the deaf)».

Optional euphemisms are opposed to taboo euphemisms based on a strict prohibition of direct nomination. «These are euphemisms related to indirect designations of intimate relationships, some physiological processes and conditions, euphemisms that replace obscene vocabulary». For example, sexual relations, the act of defecation, etc.

Euphemisms, entering into synonymous relations in the text, are able to perform stylistic functions: gradation, stylistic assessment, stylistic organization, text-forming. «Thus, euphemisms, which are stylistic synonyms, are able to perform the function of gradation, expressing varying degrees of manifestation of signs and actions». “Thanks to grading, euphemisms-synonyms convey an unequal assessment of objects, expressing a condescending attitude or a more demanding attitude: to drink, to take a sip, to suffice, to load, to shift, sort out, sip too much.”

For texts of the newspaper-journalistic style, in general, such use of euphemisms is more typical, in which their difference in stylistic characteristics is

neutralized. «Modern journalism draws euphemisms of different emotional and stylistic coloring, allows eclectic means of expression within the same text. In general, for such functional varieties as newspaper-journalistic and colloquial style, the use of euphemisms is one of the ways of presenting material associated with the expression of evaluation». «Euphemisms in thematically marked texts are included in the means of the speaker's speech strategy; are part of the means of mitigation, politeness».

Conclusion

Thus, the study of euphemisms in the prism of textual reality allows us to talk about «the expansion of the functions of euphemisms in comparison with those traditionally distinguished».

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